

Primitive Trigeminal Artery

A 29-year-old woman presented with a near-syncopal event, followed by right-sided weakness and numbness as well as dysarthria. The symptoms resolved over several hours. The patient had a history of migraine and cleidocranial dysostosis. Her work-up was negative for stroke and dissection. Computed tomographic angiography (Figure 1, A and B) showed a carotid to basilar artery anastomosis (persistent primitive trigeminal artery). This variant is present in 0.1% to 0.6% of angiograms¹. Patients with cleidocranial synostosis may be prone to anomalies of the circle of Willis since they are more likely to harbor cerebral aneurysms (26%).²

Steve M Cordina, MD
Christopher S Palmer, MD

Address correspondence to:
Steve Cordina, MD, Zeenat Qureshi Stroke Research
Center, Department of Neurology,
University of Minnesota, 420 Delaware St SE,
Minneapolis, MN 55455

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Figure 1, A and B. Computed tomographic angiography, 3-D reconstruction.

The basilar artery derives most of its blood flow from a branch (persistent trigeminal artery) that connects it to the left internal carotid artery. The left posterior cerebral artery is of fetal origin. The right vertebral artery which is not seen on these images terminated at the level of the posterior inferior cerebellar artery.

1: Internal carotid artery, 2: Middle cerebral artery, 3: Anterior cerebral artery, 4: Posterior communicating artery, 5: Posterior cerebral artery, 6: Superior cerebellar artery, 7: Persistent trigeminal artery, 8: Basilar artery, 9: Vertebral artery, 10: Sphenopalatine sinus

References

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